

Regular Expression Matching with Hashing Algebra

Mirzakhmet Syzdykov
Satbayev University, Almaty, Kazakhstan
mirzakhmets@icloud.com

ABSTRACT

We give the lowest possible bound for regular expression matching which achieves linear complexity for membership problem using the hashing technique based on the algebra of regular languages.

Keywords: regular expression, matching, hashing, algebra, optimal.

INTRODUCTION

Hashing is the most optimal technique to conduct the data dictionary [1, 2], which involves general approaches [3, 4] as well as regular expressions which are widely used for data extraction [5].

ALGORITHM

Here we give the definition of the hash-based regular expression matching on deterministic or non-deterministic finite automata: it's defined within the hash function $h(x)$ and the function computed on the finite automaton, which can lead up to the optimal speed-up, the main property of the proposed function is that it gives the whole sum on both sides like the matching pattern and given automaton for regular expression. As before the hashing matching for regular expressions was studied in a more different context, thus our algorithm works in only two steps: a) compute the hash space for accepting states in automaton and hash function for matching string; b) if both are equal, then perform the direct matching – this approach gives a speedup up to the number of unsuccessful matches in input $O(n*m)$. It's necessary that hash function $h(x)$ defined on automaton and pattern to be non-positional. The hashing function $h(x)$ is defined as follows:

$$h(a \cdot b) = h(h(a) \times h(b)), h(a+b) = h(a) \cup h(b), h(a \wedge b) = h(a) \cap h(b),$$

$$h(a \in A) = h(a), h(e) = \{0\}, h() = \{\}, h(a * a) = \{0\} \cup \sum a^i, h(a - b) = h(a), h(\neg a) = A.$$

Thus, we get a speed-up for all cases including positive matchings and our algorithm has a minimal time complexity $o(n + m)$ for the alphabet A and worst time complexity $O(n*m)$, which is a great improvement over the practically supervised cases, when the non-matching occurs more often than positive result, for the above rules the hash function is defined as non-positional as:

$$h(a \in s) = \sum |a| \bmod |A|.$$

CONCLUSION

We have also proposed the regular expression matching algorithm using hashing concept which improves the lower bound of matching to the theoretically minimal possible.

REFERENCES

1. Chi, L., & Zhu, X. (2017). Hashing techniques: A survey and taxonomy. *ACM Computing Surveys (Csur)*, 50(1), 1-36.
2. Liu, W., Wang, J., Kumar, S., & Chang, S. F. (2011). Hashing with graphs. In *Proceedings of the 28th international conference on machine learning (ICML-11)* (pp. 1-8).
3. Cheng, J., Leng, C., Wu, J., Cui, H., & Lu, H. (2014). Fast and accurate image matching with cascade hashing for 3d reconstruction. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (pp. 1-8).
4. Dalvi, N., Rastogi, V., Dasgupta, A., Das Sarma, A., & Sarlós, T. (2013, May). Optimal hashing schemes for entity matching. In *Proceedings of the 22nd international conference on world wide web* (pp. 295-306).
5. Li, Y., Krishnamurthy, R., Raghavan, S., Vaithyanathan, S., & Jagadish, H. V. (2008, October). Regular expression learning for information extraction. In *Proceedings of the 2008 conference on empirical methods in natural language processing* (pp. 21-30).